

IELTS-ASSISTANT A NEW PLATFORM FOR ORGANIZING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation : Current kunda our country across internationally recognized _ certificate provided provocative and results short term announcement to be done Linguaskill tests and training resources delivery give on affairs being performed . This certificate to teachers monthly salary ustama get , qualify increase courses ozod to be such as many opportunities provided reaches _ That's right ekan this certificates get for our above our platform to help will come

The key word : foreign languages , certificates , platform , course , language learn training , international standard , Common European Reference Framework .

May 19 this year Of our President in our country chet languages , including English teaching quality and coverage increase “ Uzbekistan In the Republic foreign languages learn popularization activities quality in terms of new stage take exit measures about decision acceptance was made . In this regard work coordination in order to Ministers Court in the presence of Foreign languages learn popularization agency formed was found . Agency activity to the beginning still a lot not while foreign languages learn popularization on effective and rejali affairs being performed .

Especially in our country chet languages at the B2 level knowing teachers up to 40 percent per month , at C1 level mastered 50 per cent for educators ustama marked . From this outside language on skills show to do for international tests list approved . Educators test costs cover for material in terms of support take possible . In the same way together , teachers malaka increase auxiliary training materials ,

including English language learn in order to books shopping to do for 1 million soums new scholarship current was made .

Only education , but a how much other directions , especially the state in the sector foreign languages knowing staff for series privileges current being done . Therefore state servants foreign til on skills development supported and the work places per week at least one day state by funded til learn training formed being done. - Foreign languages learn popularization agency 2021 Cambridge Assessment in September with english language teachers preparation , evaluation and training materials on cooperation memorandum signed , ” he said Agency directors deputy Azimjon Husanov . - Today until In Uzbekistan english tilini to know level show for approved from tests one is Linguaskill ni delivery give on agreement on together we are working . Our country across internationally recognized certificate provided provocative and results short term announcement to be done Linguaskill tests and training resources delivery give on affairs being performed . This certificate to teachers monthly salary ustama get , qualify increase courses ozod to be such as many opportunities provided reaches

Foreign languages learn popularization agency and in collaboration with Cambridge Linguaskill tests In Uzbekistan first times is used . In the future our country across millions the reader cover get planned . Linguaskill Cambridge Assessment is an English - language test that is available online carried out and speak, write, read and listen skills cover takes U til to know ability of the description international standards the results of the Common European Reference Framework (CEFR) The check is also short time and resources with easy to prepare conditions creates

English language education development on cooperation importance- Foreign languages learn popularization on the surface cooperation many of our compatriots english tilini puxta and quality assimilate help he says Azimjon Husanov . - For example for this up to local authors wrote to books interactive materials and additional sources application not done . Kelgusi training year Guess What and

Prepare by Cambridge Publishing in our country all schools training to the program is entered . Until now in our country higher education institutions login in the exams english from the tongue only grammar based on from tests we are using . However, this international standards mos not . Well , then why english tilini learn for there is resources and old approach from tests use to be continued we can do you need Therefore for both with Cambridge cooperation through Linguaskill testini current we are doing . Agency Linguaskillni our country across popularize found to be satisfactory cause - and academic degree Demand to be done not __ general , daily activity for necessary which was english language skills to try designed . This testning structure and preparation selectivity with examine we went out now our country across confidence with popularize possible . Interesting testning easy from evidence does not give . From him without hesitation bemalol use possible . Because test questions assimilated knowledge based on . We initially Linguaskill to the system via the Internet connection difficult from the past worried edik . However this different regions try internet speed _ enough degree ekaniga confidence yield we did . Next ustuvor directions Foreign languages learn popularization agency In the UN all official languages promotion to do in motion . Also our country chet languages promotion to do in order to qualify CELTA, DELTA and TKT recognition of tests and popularization the initiator was Languag learn for of education all stage advanced training applications application encouraged . That's it sample as 207 specialized at school til learn laboratories formed being done . This laboratories wide of the layer til to study attitude to change help gives

From the project the goal only to the teacher focused lesson transition style away without all in schools innovative ideas wide promotion reach and without applying consists of . In particular, our country olis regions qualifying foreign til teachers lack inobatga received without, report based on lesson transition from the system according to their skills to develop based on approach promotion reach very much important.

Foreign language organic through you did not know to the following has you can be you can :

Of course, chet languages learn as a result communicative your options expansion, more influential to work login your opportunity increase , movies and books in the original language see and reading from the possibility you have a message. But new languages assimilation you did not know other There are also aspects.

Your native language on your knowledge increases

Foreign language on their own she our language more appreciate we begin . Then from childhood to speak we started for , how it is built about often do not think his beauty we do not understand .

Concentration improves

American scientists research a how many languages knowing to people words understand on assignments gave and their tomographs observed . Results that showed that such people only one tilda to the speakers relatively, similar words good identify takes This ability different distracting factors blocking, single to the task attention focus help gives

Mathematician abilities improves

Languages in 2007 teaching American Council on by conducted research within foreign languages studying children school in the program mathematics more hour separated , but foreign languages in general unreadable to students relatively , mathematics on better results indicated detected . Surprising side no - other til the basics learn logical to think to work lowers .

You faster you will learn

Foreign language in the study new information remember stay ability This will improve reading time reduces That's it on top of that , a lot til those who know a of time in itself a lot tasks to do inclined will be .

You more enterprising you will be

Foreign language learn The essence is different people with from communication consists of . Conversation skills improvement for and , better yet , this tilda speaker or this language already examine which was people with engaged ok

CONCLUSION : Conclusion so in other words pu platform through you ieltest exams preparation if any independent interested for which it also hardens considerably .

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